

Religion in Judah

also known as “Ancient Judah”

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Entry tags: Levantine Religion, Syro-Palestinian Religion, Prophecy, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Israelite Religion, Canaanite Religions

The population of ancient Judah had, as their supreme god, YHWH. The earliest texts did not use vowels. When later texts did adopt vowels, the name of YHWH was considered too holy to vocalize. Through a misunderstanding of scribal practices, modern scholars misread the name as Yehowah/Jehovah. Today, scholarly reconstruction normalizes the name as Yahweh, though there remains some minor doubt as to its accuracy. The people of Judah (Judahites, sometimes referred to as Judeans/Judaeans, though this better represents the region under later Roman occupation) were predominantly highland people who derived from the broader ethnic category of "Canaanites." Pastoralism and highland agriculture (vineyards, olive orchards, some grains, etc.) were the norm. Being situated in the southern Levant (eastern Mediterranean seaboard), Judah occupied an ancient crossroads and often felt the pull and dominance of Egypt and/or Mesopotamia. Judah, as a polity, only gained a firm identity during a period when those greater political centres had directed their attention elsewhere. The highlands also afforded Judah some measure of protection as well as isolation. The official religion of Judah was centred on the capital city, Jerusalem, where there was the official temple dedicated to YHWH. As with other ancient temples, this temple was also a site for royal administration, and may have supported the local scribal culture. Priests oversaw offerings, including both animal and vegetative offerings, and prophets proclaimed their messages publicly. Festivals were most likely linked originally to the agricultural calendar, though later they became attached to the cultural memory of certain events in Judah's past. Two of the thorniest issues in evaluating Judah's religion are Judah's identity vis-à-vis Israel and the actual religion of Judahites obscured by the ancient sources, namely the Hebrew Bible/Tanakh/Old Testament (hereafter HB). The HB presents Judah as having been part of Israel from its founding ancestors. Our earliest non-biblical sources, however, display two neighbouring kingdoms, Judah and Israel, with Israel being the more powerful. Modern historians often doubt that Judah had been part of Israel, but instead had later assumed Israel's identity when the kingdom of Israel was destroyed by the Assyrians in the late 8th century BCE. The HB comes to us via Judah, though undoubtedly some of the material originated in Israel. Therefore, it is difficult to disentangle Judah from Israel in reconstruction. Many of the religious aspects assigned to "all Israel" (including Judah in the HB) may not have been practiced in Judah. According to the HB, Israel and Judah had formed what is often called the "United Monarchy" under Saul, David, and then Solomon, with "all Israel (including Judah)" being ruled from Jerusalem. After Solomon (c. 930 BCE), the HB says that the kingdom of (all) Israel, split into two kingdoms: Israel in the north, with capitals that changed with dynastic changes, and Judah in the south, centred at Jerusalem and housing the dynastic line of David. Therefore, studies of Judah as a distinct identity is sometimes given dates as early as mid-11th century BCE if including the HB's "all Israel," or beginning from c. 930 BCE, when the HB says Judah and Israel split. Others, relying primarily on archaeology, will begin meaningful discussion in the 9th century BCE when we begin to see more non-biblical attestations to the kingdom of Judah. The second issue, regarding sanctioned religion, is also obscured by the HB. The texts we have are the largest source of information about Judah, but they were curated and edited heavily by scribes of a certain theological position. There is evidence of difference beneath the surface. Archaeology, even more so, shows a wide variety of religious practices either not described in the HB or condemned therein. Various other gods received worship (Asherah, Baal, El, et al.), and other religious officials presided over other religious shrines (not in Jerusalem). Household religion and ancestor worship also seem to have proliferated in Judah. Of these aspects, however, we have less

information and scholarship is usually suggestive rather than certain.

Date Range: 1000 BCE - 586 BCE

Region: Ancient Judah

Region tags: Eastern Mediterranean, Levant, Israel, Palestine

Ancient Judah at its greatest extent (South and West borders particularly flexible)

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Albertz, Rainer. *A History of Israelite Religion in the Old Testament Period: From the Beginnings to the End of the Monarchy* (vol. 1). Westminster John Knox Press, 1994.
- Source 2: Niditch, Susan. *Ancient Israelite Religion*. Oxford Univ. Press, 1997.
- Source 3: Keel, Othmar. *Jerusalem and the One God: A Religious History*. Fortress Press, 2017.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.bibleodyssey.org/places/main-articles/kingdom-of-judah>
- Source 1 Description: Brief history of Judah and its connection to religion of Israel
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.bibleodyssey.org/people/related-articles/monotheism-in-the-hebrew-bible>
- Source 2 Description: Discusses the rise of monotheism in Israel/Judah and connection to the Hebrew Bible

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.bibleodyssey.org/bibles>
- Source 1 Description: Searchable Bibles (2 of 3 include Christian New Testament) in English
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.mechon-mamre.org/>
- Source 2 Description: Hebrew Bible in ancient Hebrew. Also has parallel Hebrew-English and Hebrew-French

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The scriptures as we know them (the Hebrew Bible/Tanakh/Old Testament) date from after

Ancient Judah was no more. However, much of the material in the scripture had its origins in the time of the kingdom of Judah's existence, and some perhaps earlier. Scholars speculate as to what was available and in use within Judah during its existence, but there is little certainty. Compounding the problem is that some of the material may have come from the correct time period, but may have originated instead in the kingdom of Israel (northern neighbour) and only later incorporated into Judah's scriptures

↳ Are they written:
– Yes

↳ Are they oral:
– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:
– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:
– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:
– No

↳ Inspired by high god:
– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:
– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:
– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:
– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:
– Yes

Notes: Scribes edited heavily until a few centuries after Judah's demise (586 BCE)

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Notes: During the time of the kingdom of Judah, no. Centuries later a codified canon developed.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Notable religious competition with Assyrians who claim supremacy of their god over that of Judah (701 BCE)

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Certain groups within Judah accommodate religion from outsiders (e.g. rituals associated with Mesopotamian deity Tammuz)

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: Often "live and let live" interactions with external religious groups

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Religious reforms of Hezekiah (c.700) and Josiah (late 7th century BCE) hint at conflict that may have been violent. Certainly in Israel there was conflict described in the Hebrew Bible between Elijah (prophet of Yahweh) and the prophets of Baal and Asherah

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Most notably from the Assyrians.

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 250

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 14

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 35

Notes: The temple precincts at the time of construction (according to the Hebrew Bible's temple origin story) made up about 1/3 of Jerusalem's built up area. The city later grew, at which point the temple precincts probably accounted for approximately 15% of built up area.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 90

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: Through a form of taxation, and perhaps from the crown.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: This varies. The king seems to have a special relationship to the deity (YHWH), especially with characters such as David, Solomon, Hezekiah, but there is a separate high priest who is perhaps more accurately considered to be the head of the religion.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Yes

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– No

Notes: Perhaps this could be true if one is considering the few non-Judahites present, but we have scant information about them. Many are hidden in the texts and archaeological record as enslaved people.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– I don't know

Notes: According to the Hebrew Bible (edited later), iconography was forbidden. But the HB also contains many stories of illicit images being used, both at home and in public religious settings. Most of these were dedicated to deities other than YHWH (official god of Judah), but some may have focused on YHWH as well

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– I don't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– Yes

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– No

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Insofar as the official religion was enforceable throughout the region, the high priest oversaw said religion

Membership/Group Interactions

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Architecture, Geography

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Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– I don't know

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it

relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

- ↳ Food:

– Yes

- ↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

- ↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

- ↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: bestiality; and male-male intercourse

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: anthropomorphism declines throughout the period and beyond. See Mark Smith
Where the Gods Are

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: Often YHWH is associated with the sky/heavens, including in imagery of a storm

god, but is not limited to that domain.

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
 - Notes: There may be hints of such a thing in the murky pre-history of Israel/Judah, but such a notion is highly speculative
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample

region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: This idea also is in development, from regionally restricted to supra regional, during the time of Judah

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
 - ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- Notes: In Judah's scriptures, their heroic forbears received direct communication from YHWH, and perhaps some kings did. There is also a story of a prophet

(Amos) who was called to be a prophet (religious specialist) even though it was not his occupation. It is unclear, however, whether average people could expect that YHWH would appear to them or otherwise communicate with them directly. It was assumed to come through specialists.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: If they choose, angels may appear (usually "Angel of YHWH" whose identity is difficult to disentangle from YHWH's own identity)

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Difficult to say. It depends if one includes dead ancestors as well as angels, both of which have scant evidence for this time period

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– I don't know

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– I don't know

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– I don't know

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: This seems to develop later. Otherwise, the shadowy afterlife (Sheol) seems to wait for everyone.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: Perhaps if a disease is considered to be such displeasure

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Most scholars would argue that resurrection theology begins to develop in Judaism centuries after the destruction of the kingdom of Judah

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– I don't know

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– I don't know

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– I don't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– I don't know

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– I don't know

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Evidence of silver scrolls citing texts later associated with Judah's scriptures (Ketef Hinnom excavation)

↳ Other grave goods:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– I don't know

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– No

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– No

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– No

Notes: Economic redistribution rather than charitable giving (though the latter is still encouraged)

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– No

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– No

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– No

↳ Cooperation:

– No

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– No

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– No

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– No

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– No

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– No

↳ Optimism / hope:

– No

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– No

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– I don't know

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Most scholars would argue that resurrection theology begins to develop in Judaism centuries after the destruction of the kingdom of Judah

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– I don't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– I don't know

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– I don't know

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Evidence of silver scrolls citing texts later associated with Judah's scriptures (Ketef Hinnom excavation)

↳ Other grave goods:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– I don't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: anthropomorphism declines throughout the period and beyond. See Mark Smith *Where the Gods Are*

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: Often YHWH is associated with the sky/heavens, including in imagery of a storm god, but is not limited to that domain.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
 - Notes: There may be hints of such a thing in the murky pre-history of Israel/Judah, but such a notion is highly speculative
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes

Notes: This idea also is in development, from regionally restricted to supra regional, during the time of Judah

- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - I don't know

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
 - Notes: In Judah's scriptures, their heroic forbears received direct communication from YHWH, and perhaps some kings did. There is also a story of a prophet (Amos) who was called to be a prophet (religious specialist) even though it was not his occupation. It is unclear, however, whether average people could expect that YHWH would appear to them or otherwise communicate with them directly. It was assumed to come through specialists.

- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No

↳ Other form of communication with living:
– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
– Yes

Notes: If they choose, angels may appear (usually "Angel of YHWH" whose identity is difficult to disentangle from YHWH's own identity)

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Difficult to say. It depends if one includes dead ancestors as well as angels, both of which have scant evidence for this time period

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
– Yes

↳ Adultery:
– Yes

↳ Incest:
– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:
– Yes [specify]: bestiality; and male-male intercourse

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - I don't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god:
 - I don't know

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– I don't know

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– I don't know

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– I don't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: This seems to develop later. Otherwise, the shadowy afterlife (Sheol) seems to wait for everyone.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: Perhaps if a disease is considered to be such displeasure

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– I don't know

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
– I don't know

↳ Done randomly:
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– No

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– No

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– No

Notes: Economic redistribution rather than charitable giving (though the latter is still encouraged)

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– No

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– No

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - No
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - No
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - No

- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - No
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - No
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - No

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

Notes: Perhaps in the sense that sacrificing an animal in a burnt offering is destruction, then yes.

↳ Other:

–Yes [specify]: Sacrifice to deity out of one's property

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: These rituals are mostly unknown, although comparative material from nearby contemporary cultures strongly suggests that there was at least some household religious activity. It may have been related to YHWH (chief god), but perhaps not. It likely involved the veneration of ancestors, and also something that relates to the so-called "pillar figurines" that have been attributed (too simplistically) to "fertility" rites.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
– Yes
Notes: Most likely

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– I don't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:
– No

↳ Circumcision:
– Yes

Notes: Circumcision doesn't take place at these gatherings (communal festivals) as far as we know, but males are supposed to be circumcised already

↳ Food taboos:
– Yes

↳ Hair:
– No

↳ Dress:
– No

↳ Ornaments:
– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:
– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:
– Yes

Notes: Question is unclear to me. But all Judahites were supposed to have been from a common ancestor, and at one generation higher were descended from a common ancestor of all Israel (namely Jacob=Israel)

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:
– No

Notes: non-Judahite residents whose ancestry is from a distant land would not be included. Other foreigners from nearby peoples (excluding Philistines) were construed as being simply more distant kin (e.g. Moabites, Ammonites, Edomites)

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:
– No

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

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Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

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– No

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– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

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Notes: Perhaps in the sense that sacrificing an animal in a burnt offering is destruction, then yes.

↳ Other:

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– Field doesn't know

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Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
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↳ Hair:

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↳ Dress:

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Notes: non-Judahite residents whose ancestry is from a distant land would not be included. Other foreigners from nearby peoples (excluding Philistines) were construed as being simply more distant kin (e.g. Moabites, Ammonites, Edomites)

- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:
– No

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

- A chiefdom

Notes: A formal monarchy. Perhaps in the later period of the monarchy (7th-6th centuries BCE) there were "nobles" of a sort, but generally the distinctions were likely fluid and power was attached to the monarchy and its hangers-on, and somewhat in the priesthood. There also seems to have developed an urban/rural divide, or Jerusalem/rest of Judah divide, but this is not certain. Some other cities seem to have been significant, such as Lachish.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

- Field doesn't know

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

- No

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

- Yes

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

- I don't know

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

- Yes

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

- No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

- Yes

- ↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: Debatable whether they have "their own" written language. Nearby peoples shared at least a very similar language and writing system, though some things are characteristically Judahite

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: Difficult to separate "state" from religion

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: It is difficult to separate "state" and "religious" bureaucracies, though both are present

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: When they are occupied by the Assyrians and later the Babylonians

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: The HB claims that at one point in the 9th century BCE a king tried to implement religious judges in the land. But there is no other evidence of this happening, to my knowledge.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: It is unlikely that it was practiced, at least not regularly, but the HB speaks of voluntary slavery as a term of servitude to pay off one's debts. One is supposed to be released from slavery after 7 years. There is also the larger scale Jubilee, supposedly to be celebrated every 50 years, where slaves are freed and everyone receives back and returns to their ancestral inheritance. In effect, it resembles an economic restart button. There is little to no evidence of this actually ever being practiced, however. Judea in the Roman period seems to have alms for poverty relief, but it is difficult to determine when that began.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "Institutional" might be too strong to describe the role of elders in a given town who preside over daily cases. Other leaders are also said to have sat in the gate (town square) to provide judgement in disputes.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: via the voluntary debt slavery discussed in the above question

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: This is very debatable. First, one must ask whether the extant texts of the HB actually form a legal code as such, or whether they are of another genre. Second, one must ask when they were composed (and where), because they may date from after the fall of Judah or from a neighbouring location. Third, even if one could call the texts a code and confirm that they were composed in Judah during the requisite time period, it is uncertain whether they would have been practiced, or whether they represented more of a priestly/scrival ideal. There is also the case of the judges sent out in the 9th century (mentioned in earlier question about judges) who, if the story is historical, would have brought some form of legal code with them

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: difficult to separate "state" from religion

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: A formal monarchy. Perhaps in the later period of the monarchy (7th-6th centuries BCE) there were "nobles" of a sort, but generally the distinctions were likely fluid and power was attached to the monarchy and its hangers-on, and somewhat in the priesthood. There also seems to have developed an urban/rural divide, or Jerusalem/rest of Judah divide, but this is not certain. Some other cities seem to have been significant, such as Lachish.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: It is unlikely that it was practiced, at least not regularly, but the HB speaks of voluntary slavery as a term of servitude to pay off one's debts. One is supposed to be released from slavery after 7 years. There is also the larger scale Jubilee, supposedly to be celebrated every 50 years, where slaves are freed and everyone receives back and returns to their ancestral inheritance. In effect, it resembles an economic restart button. There is little to no evidence of this actually ever being practiced, however. Judea in the Roman period seems to have alms for poverty relief, but it is difficult to determine when that began.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: via the voluntary debt slavery discussed in the above question

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: It is difficult to separate "state" and "religious" bureaucracies, though both are present

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– I don't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in

question:

– I don't know

Notes: Difficult to separate "state" from religion

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: The HB claims that at one point in the 9th century BCE a king tried to implement religious judges in the land. But there is no other evidence of this happening, to my knowledge.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "Institutional" might be too strong to describe the role of elders in a given town who preside over daily cases. Other leaders are also said to have sat in the gate (town square) to provide judgement in disputes.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: This is very debatable. First, one must ask whether the extant texts of the HB actually form a legal code as such, or whether they are of another genre. Second, one must ask when they were composed (and where), because they may date from after the fall of Judah or from a neighbouring location. Third, even if one could call the texts a code and confirm that they were composed in Judah during the requisite time period, it is uncertain whether they would have been practiced, or whether they represented more of a priestly/scrival ideal. There is also the case of the judges sent out in the 9th century (mentioned in earlier question about judges) who, if the story is historical, would have brought

some form of legal code with them

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: difficult to separate "state" from religion

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– I don't know

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: When they are occupied by the Assyrians and later the Babylonians

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: Debatable whether they have "their own" written language. Nearby peoples shared at least a very similar language and writing system, though some things are characteristically Judahite

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

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